

Light modulation from the IFOV repositioning

by L Lindegren (1983 Feb 16)

The IFOV repositioning frequency proposed by MATRA, $1/T_2 = 150$ Hz, coincides exactly with the nominal light modulation frequency v/s ($v = 180$ as/s, $s = 1.2$ as). In each repositioning interval (dwell segment), the IFOV is stationary w.r.t. the grid, while the star moves a short distance $vT_2 = 1.2$ as. This produces some extra light modulation at 150 Hz and multiples thereof, unless the IFOV profile (convolved with the star image profile on the photocathode) is very flat. This will most likely result in a biased location estimate for as long as the grid modulation and the IFOV repositioning have constant phase difference.

The size of this effect can be appreciated from a simplified model. Consider a single modulation period $-\pi < \psi < \pi$ with an ideal modulation (infinite IFOV) of the form

$$I(\psi) = 1 + M \cos(\psi - \psi_0) \quad (1)$$

Here, ψ_0 is the true modulation phase, corresponding to the true location of the star. The extra modulation introduced by the IFOV is taken to be the factor

$$f(\psi) = 1 + a\psi \quad -\pi < \psi < \pi \quad (2)$$

The total signal is $I(\psi)f(\psi)$, and the resulting phase error can be computed as

$$\delta = \text{ATAN2} \left[\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} I(\psi)f(\psi) \sin \psi d\psi, \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} I(\psi)f(\psi) \cos \psi d\psi \right] - \psi_0 = \quad (3)$$

$$= \arctan \frac{2a \cos \psi_0 - \frac{1}{2}aM \cos(2\psi_0)}{M + 2a \sin \psi_0 - \frac{1}{2}aM \sin(2\psi_0)} \quad (4)$$

We have

$$|\delta| \lesssim 2a(M^{-1} + 0.25) \quad (5)$$

Let α be the slope of the IFOV profile in magnitudes per arcsec. We find

$$a \approx \frac{0.4 \ln 10}{2\pi} \alpha s \quad (6)$$

and since the positional bias is $b = (s/2\pi)\delta$,

$$|b| \lesssim \frac{0.4 \ln 10}{2\pi^2} (M^{-1} + 0.25) s^2 \alpha \approx (0.12 \text{ as}^2/\text{mag}) \alpha \quad (7)$$

with $s = 1.2 \text{ as}$ and $M = 0.65$. For $|b| < 1 \text{ mas}$, we should have $\alpha < 0.008 \text{ mag/as}$.

If the IFOV profile provided by ESTEC (letter by Bonnefoy, 1982 Dec 23) is plotted in magnitudes versus the linear distance, it is seen that $\alpha \sim 0.03 \text{ mag/as}$ already for an offset of some 5 as , corresponding to $|b| < 4 \text{ mas}$. The effect may be worse if the extended star image is taken into account.

In order to eliminate the effect, or at least reduce it substantially, the grid modulation frequency v/s should be shifted away from 150 Hz . The minimum shift required to separate the frequencies at frame level is determined by the frame bandwidth $1/T_4 \approx 0.5 \text{ Hz}$. But since the scanning speed v may deviate by up to 2% from the nominal value, one should have at least a difference of 3.5 Hz . E.g. $v/s = 153.85 \text{ Hz}$ (nominally) could be achieved by reducing the grid period to $s = 1.17 \text{ as}$.

